

X-ROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D6.2

Modelled LCoE for the X-Rotor

 <https://X-Rotor-project.eu>

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://X-Rotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

The objective of Deliverable 6.2: “Modelled LCoE for the X-rotor” is to provide estimates of the X-Rotor **Levelised Cost of Energy (LCoE)**. This report employs an LCoE tool adapted by UCC from their LEANWIND financial model (Devoy McAuliffe, et al., 2018) (Judge, et al., 2019). The tool and LCoE methodology are presented in Section 2. The calculation will consider detailed CAPEX and OPEX estimates for the X-Rotor concept (XRC). The University of Strathclyde have used their O&M model to determine the maintenance costs considering a primitive and a partially optimised O&M strategy. CAPEX estimates for a 5MW X-Rotor have been derived based on standard HAWT estimates. However, it should be noted that these are preliminary and turbine CAPEX will be updated in D6.3 as WP4 progresses and XROTOR specific estimates are made available to WP6.

This deliverable considers a baseline scenario to determine the X-Rotor LCoE assuming a 5MW turbine, a 500MW farm, 100km from shore (Section 3 and 4). A series of sensitivity studies are also applied (Section 5) to determine projected costs for 2030, assess the impact of extending the operational lifetime, optimising the O&M scenario, and considering different site locations/distance from shore. Section 6 provides an XRC LCoE estimate (derived from HAWT CAPEX inputs) with section 7 summarising the deliverable, results and further work to be completed in the final WP6 deliverable (D6.3).

List of acronyms

O&M	Operation and Maintenance
LCoE	Levelised Costs of Energy
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
WP	Work Package
XRC	X-ROTOR concept
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OWF	Offshore Wind Farm
WT	Wind Turbine
HAWT	Horizontal-Axis Wind Turbine
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
VAWT	Vertical-Axis Wind Turbine
mr	Minor Repair
Mr	Major Repair
MR	Major Replacement

1 Introduction

The X-Rotor project is developing an innovative wind turbine design that will target cost reductions and scalability. The “X-Rotor offshore wind turbine” is a Vertical Axis Wind Turbine (VAWT) /Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine (HAWT) hybrid. It is expected that the X-Rotor concept could reduce Levelised Cost of Energy (LCoE) by 20-30% by providing a:

- 25-50% reduction in OPEX (Operations and Maintenance expenditure) through no heavy components or machinery being situated at a great height above sea-water and through general simplification of the turbine. This reduces the requirement for costly heavy lift vessels for maintenance. The design also removes failure modes around the gearbox, multi-pole generator and yaw system.
- 5-25% reduction in CAPEX (Capital expenditure) by reducing the cost of drive-trains through an easily scalable approach to power take-off that does not require a gearbox or a multi-pole generator whilst achieving comparable efficiency levels in power conversion.

Having a low centre of mass with no heavy machinery at height, may make it particularly well-suited to floating offshore usage. Whilst the X-Rotor offers floating wind benefits, it should be noted that technical analysis of the X-Rotor’s floating potential is outside the scope of this project.

The objective of this deliverable is to provide estimates of the X-Rotor Levelised Cost of Energy (LCoE). This report employs an LCoE tool adapted by UCC from their LEANWIND financial model (Devoy McAuliffe, et al., 2018) (Judge, et al., 2019). The tool and LCoE methodology are presented in Section 2. The calculation will consider detailed CAPEX and OPEX estimates for the X-Rotor concept (XRC). The University of Strathclyde have used their O&M model to determine the maintenance costs considering a primitive and a partially optimised O&M strategy. CAPEX estimates for a 5MW X-Rotor have been derived based on standard HAWT estimates. However, it should be noted that these are preliminary and will be updated in D6.3 as WP4 progresses and XROTOR specific CAPEX estimates are made available to WP6.

This deliverable considers a baseline scenario to determine the X-Rotor LCoE assuming a 5MW turbine, a 500MW farm, 100km from shore (Section 3 and 4). A series of sensitivity studies are also applied (Section 5) to determine projected costs for 2030, assess the impact of extending the operational lifetime, optimising the O&M scenario, and considering different site locations/distance from shore. Section 6 provides an XRC LCoE estimate (derived from HAWT CAPEX inputs) with section 7 summarising the deliverable, results and further work to be completed in the final WP6 deliverable (D6.3).

2 X-ROTOR LCoE Tool

The EU FP7 LEANWIND project developed a financial assessment tool in excel to determine the LCoE of a given offshore wind farm scenario. This has been updated and adapted for the X-Rotor project and is hereafter referred to as “the LCoE tool”.

LCoE can be defined as the price of electricity required to “breakeven”, i.e. capital and annual costs are covered. This can be calculated in a number of different ways, including/excluding different costs as outlined in (Devoy McAuliffe F. N., 2021). The most common method used essentially considers the total lifetime costs (using a pre-tax project cash flow) divided by the total energy produced. These are discounted to determine the present value of future cash flows (i.e. the Net Present Value (NPV)) by a discount rate. The rate is selected by the user based on a number of criteria as outlined in Section 2.3. A full explanation of the LCoE calculation method used in this tool is provided in section 2.8.

The following provides an overview of the LCoE tool inputs and outputs with brief explanations, equations and definitions of the different terminology where needed.

2.1 Overview

The LCoE tool is in excel and comprises 6 tabs to input information (Section 2.2-2.7); 1 cashflow tab (section 2.8) to process the inputs; a Results tab (Section 2.9) that summarises the scenario inputs and outputs. Input tab cells are colour coded for users to indicate where an input value is essential; possible but not necessary to produce a results; auto-calculated from other inputs using a formula; or if the user must select from a list of options. The cell legend provided in the tool “Instructions” tab is illustrated in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 Cell legend

	Input value essential
	Input value possible but not necessary
xxxx	Cell value calculated by formula
	Select from list

2.2 Project

Table 2.2 illustrates the input values for the project tab.

Table 2.2 Project

Project inputs	Units	Value
Project Name	<i>text</i>	
Site Location	<i>text</i>	
Project Lifetime	<i>years</i>	
Farm Capacity	<i>GW</i>	
Fixed/Floating	<i>select</i>	
Water depth	<i>m</i>	
Site area	<i>km²</i>	
Distance to grid connection	<i>km</i>	
Distance to port - installation	<i>km</i>	
Distance to port - O&M	<i>km</i>	
Commissioning year	xxxx	

The **Project Lifetime** refers to the operational project life. **Commissioning year** refers to the year the project became operational. None of the inputs in this tab are strictly required for the calculations. However, it is recommended that the user inputs a name and then saves a copy of the tool using this title in order to clearly store a scenario for future reference.

2.3 Finance

Table 2.3 illustrates the input values for the financial assumptions.

Table 2.3 Finance

Financial inputs	Units	Value
Electricity price (constant)	€	
Real discount rate	%	
Loan Amount (Debt)	€	
Debt Interest Rate	%	
Loan Term	years	
Loan start year	year	
Loan administration charges	%	
Tax rate	%	

Capital allowance rate	%	
------------------------	---	--

The **Electricity Price** is only required if the user wishes to calculate the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) or NPV (see Section 2.9). In the current version of the tool, the **Tax rate** is also only relevant when the users is calculating IRR, NPV etc. since it must know the revenue in order to calculate the tax. Although some LCoE calculations may consider the tax payments as a cost, this is not a feature of this LCoE tool. The **Capital allowance rate** represents the depreciation on the capital investments and is tax deductible so may also be considered where tax is being considered within the IRR and NPV calculation.

The **Loan Amount** refers to the project debt e.g. if 70% of the investment cost is borrowed, this is 70% of the CAPEX. The **Debt Interest Rate** is the interest rate that is owed on repayments. The **Loan Term** is the loan repayment period and the **Loan start year** is the year in the project when repayments begin. **Loan administration charges** are an additional % cost of managing the loan.

A **discount rate** is the risk-adjusted opportunity-cost of capital (Levitt, Kempton, Smith, Musial, & Firestone, 2011). Some base it on a Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) considering the debt-equity ratio used to finance the project as per Equation 1.

Equation 1

$$WACC = (CoD * \% \text{ of debt}) + (CoE * \% \text{ of equity})$$

Others would seek to apply the IRR, i.e. the discount rate at which the project has an NPV of zero and is generally used to make an investment decision. Therefore, it tends to be higher than the WACC discount rate as investors will be risk-adverse and include a buffer in addition to the cost of capital.

A Real LCoE is determined by applying an inflation-adjusted (**real**) **discount rate** to a cash flow of real costs that do not contain the effects of inflation. It can be derived from a nominal rate and vice versa using the following formula in equations 2 and 3:

Equation 2

$$r_{Real} = [(1 + r_{Nominal}) / (1 + \text{inflation rate})] - 1$$

Equation 3

$$r_{Nominal} = [(1 + r_{Real}) * (1 + \text{inflation rate})] - 1$$

2.4 CAPEX

Table 2.4 illustrates the input values for Capital or Investment cost (CAPEX) assumptions.

Table 2.4 CAPEX

CAPEX inputs	Units	Value
Project development and management	€	
Turbine Capacity	MW	
Cost per turbine	€	
Number of Turbines	number	
Substructure Type	select	
Cost per substructure	€	
Offshore Substation Yes/No	select	
Offshore Substation capacity	MW	
Offshore Substation cost	€	
Inter-Array (IA) cable rating	kV	
IA cable length (total)	km	

IA cost per km	€	
Export cable rating	kV	
Number of export cables	number	
Export cable length (total)	km	
Export cable cost per km	€	
Onshore substation & grid connection	€	
Assembly and installation	€	
Project commissioning	€	
Contingency, construction finance and insurance	€	
Site lease	€	
Total CAPEX	€	

The **Substructure Cost** should include mooring lines and anchoring when a floating turbine is being considered. The **IA and Export cabling length** should be the total length (km). Users should note that while the cost figure cells are in yellow (essential), they may not actually be needed. However, for a comprehensive CAPEX estimate, these are the main categories the user should consider. Therefore, it is advised that each cell is considered when inputting values.

2.5 OPEX

Table 2.5 illustrates the input values for Operational and Maintenance expenditure (OPEX).

Table 2.5 OPEX

OPEX inputs	Units	Value
Average annual maintenance costs	€	
Fixed annual operation costs	€	
Total Annual OPEX	€	

Maintenance costs refer to the variable cost associated with scheduled Preventive Maintenance (PM) and Corrective Maintenance (CM) activities, triggered by turbine failures.

Operation costs refer to fixed OPEX costs associated with farm operational expenditure e.g. staffing, renting office space, spare parts storage, annual insurance etc.

2.6 Energy Production

Table 2.6 illustrates the input values for energy production.

Table 2.6 Energy Production

Energy production inputs	Units	Value
Theoretical Annual Energy Production	MWh/year	
Average Annual Energy Production	MWh/year	
Net Capacity Factor	%	
Availability	%	

The **Capacity Factor** considers the energy production, divided by the **theoretical energy production** of a device/farm operating at maximum rated capacity over a period of time. **Net Capacity Factor** means that the estimated production includes downtime due to maintenance/failures. Downtime is time when the turbine is not producing/only partially producing energy.

Availability refers to the amount of time the farm is “available” to produce energy over a period divided by the amount of time in that period. This is **time-based**, however, some people may also

calculate **energy-based** availability. The latter considers the energy produced including production losses due to downtime over a period, divided by the energy that could have been produced during that time with no downtime. This should not be confused with the capacity factor as defined above.

2.7 Decommissioning

Table 2.7 illustrates the input values for decommissioning cost and salvage revenue assumptions.

Table 2.7 Decommissioning

Decommissioning inputs	Units	Value
Decommissioning	€	
Salvage revenue	€	
Total Decommissioning	€	

The user can input decommissioning costs but also salvage revenue that will offset expenditure. However, these are not required inputs and LCoE calculations often include decommissioning costs as part of a “bond” included in the capital expenditure.

2.8 Cashflow

This tab utilises the inputs in a comprehensive cashflow analysis considering the following sections:

- Energy production
- Cash Inflows
- Cash Outflows
- Projected Profit and Loss
- Cashflow

The cashflow uses Equation 4 to calculate the LCoE as per the abbreviations in Table 2.8.

Equation 4

$$LCoE = \frac{I + \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{LP}{(1+r)^k} + \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{INT}{(1+r)^k} + \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{A^k}{(1+r)^k} + \sum_{d=n+1}^f \frac{(D^d - S^d)}{(1+r)^d}}{\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{E^k}{(1+r)^k}}$$

Table 2.8 Equation 1 Abbreviations

d	year in post-project decommissioning	E	Energy produced
k	year in project lifetime	I	Investment costs
n	project lifetime	INT	Interest payment
r	discount rate	LCoE	Levelised Cost of Energy
A	Annual costs	LP	Loan Payment
C	Cash Flow	S	Salvage Revenue
D	Decommissioning costs		

Table 2.9 outlines the key outputs calculated based on the inputs in Section 2.2-2.7 and using the cashflow sheet described above.

Table 2.9 Cashflow results summary

Costs		€
Energy		kWh
Real LCOE		€/kWh
Real LCOE		€/MWh

NPV		€
IRR		%

Where the user knows/can estimate the cost of electricity (section 2.3) and would like to calculate the IRR (equation 5) e.g. to apply as the discount rate. Where the user inputs the electricity price, they can also consider tax and capital allowance rates (as discussed in section 2.3).

Equation 5

$$NPV(0) = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{C_k}{(1 + IRR)^k}$$

2.9 Results

Table 2.10 illustrates how the tool provides an overview of the key inputs and the Results including discounted and undiscounted costs and energy production.

Table 2.10 Project summary

Project Input Summary			Project Results Summary		
Project Name	<i>text</i>		Project Costs	€	
Site Location	<i>text</i>		Discounted Project Costs	€	
Project Lifetime	<i>years</i>		Energy Production	<i>MWh</i>	
Farm Capacity	<i>GW</i>		Discounted Energy	<i>MWh</i>	
Real discount rate	<i>%</i>		Real LCOE	<i>€/kWh</i>	
Loan Amount (Debt)	<i>€</i>		Real LCOE	<i>€/MWh</i>	
Debt Interest Rate	<i>%</i>		NPV	€	
Loan Term	<i>years</i>		IRR	%	
Loan start year	<i>year</i>				
Loan administration charges	<i>%</i>				
Tax rate	<i>%</i>				
Capital allowance rate	<i>%</i>				
CAPEX	<i>€</i>				
Annual Average OPEX	<i>€</i>				
Decommissioning	<i>€</i>				
Average Annual Energy Production	<i>MWh/year</i>				
Net Capacity Factor	<i>%</i>				
Availability	<i>%</i>				

3 Baseline Scenario – Inputs

The purpose of this deliverable is to model the LCoE for the XRC. This section provides an overview of the baseline scenario inputs.

3.1 Project description

The project consists of 100 x 5MW XRCs (500MW farm capacity). The site is a hypothetical North Sea site, using Metocean data from FINO3 to model the O&M operations and power production (Anderson & Carroll, 2023). The distance to port is 100km. The XRC is assumed to be fixed-

bottomed, but the substructure is not a key area of analysis. A generic monopile is considered across all analysis based on (Stehly & Duffy, 2022) and scaled in terms of cost for a 5MW turbine.

3.2 CAPEX

The XRC 5MW turbine cost (€1,182/kW) is broken down in Table 3.1. This was estimated using (Fingersh, Hand, & Laxson, 2006) and applying scaling laws. An additional amount is added for assembly, wind turbine supplier aspects of installation and commissioning, profit and warranty based on (BVG Associates, 2019).

Table 3.1 5MW 2 x vertical blades

Rotor	2,347,042
	<i>Blades (4)</i> 1,912,634
	<i>Hub</i> 109,066
	<i>Pitch System</i> 138,104
	<i>Low Speed Shaft</i> 13,203
	<i>Cross Member</i> 11,499
	<i>Main Bearing</i> 162,535
Tower	506,228
Break/coupling	11,339
Generator	370,500
Power Converter	450,300
Nacelle cover	69,611
Secondary rotors	15,330
Electrical Power take-off	168,000
Assembly, wind turbine supplier aspects of installation & commissioning, profit and warranty	1,972,000
Total	5,910,350

The Balance of System (BoS) and Soft CAPEX costs are based on NREL’s 2021 estimated costs for a representative fixed offshore wind farm installed in the US North Atlantic (Stehly & Duffy, 2022). This is illustrated in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1 NREL 2021 fixed-bottom Offshore Wind System CAPEX breakdown

Costs were converted from dollars (\$) to euro (€) assuming a rate of \$1 = €0.91 and scaled from the NREL 600MW reference farm (75 x 8MW) to the XRC baseline scenario (100 x 5MW). Figures are presented in Table 3.2. Costs are sorted from highest to lowest.

Table 3.2 BoS and Soft CAPEX – Baseline Scenario

Electrical infrastructure	315,315,000
Contingency, construction finance, insurance during construction	251,160,000
Substructure and foundation	225,680,000
Assembly and installation	185,640,000
Lease price	80,990,000
Development and project management	41,405,000
Plant commissioning	15,470,000

A variation between the (Stehly & Duffy, 2022) and XRC baseline assumptions is that the latter does not include the decommissioning costs (€106.47/kW) in the CAPEX. These are added in the final year of the project cash flow, discounted to consider their future value.

It should be noted that since a significant proportion of the costs used are taken from (Stehly & Duffy, 2022), which were based on 2021 figures. Therefore, it is also assumed that the XRC baseline scenario was commissioned in 2021.

Figure 3.2 presents a full CAPEX breakdown for the XRC baseline scenario. The turbine comprises the largest proportion (35%). It is a key area that should be focused on for future design optimisation and cost reduction.

Figure 3.2 CAPEX breakdown – baseline scenario

3.3 OPEX

The O&M strategy for the XRC baseline scenario was modelled using the Strathclyde O&M tool and is outlined in D6.1 (Anderson & Carroll, 2023). Failure rates, repair durations and costs are detailed

in D6.1; however, the scenarios were re-run for this deliverable (D6.2) with some small updates in the assumptions. The following summarises the baseline, conservative O&M strategy:

- The hypothetical wind farm has 5 Crew Transfer Vessels (CTV), and a pool of 30 technicians.
- Minor repairs are assigned to CTVs and are addressed offshore.
- The secondary HAWTs are assumed to be modular, and when a generator fails, the module is removed and replaced by a Service Operations Vessel (SOV). The shift from Fast Supply Vessels (FSV) used in D6.2 analysis to SOVs is explained below. SOVs are hired on a fix-on-fail basis for secondary HAWT module generator replacements.
- When one of the secondary HAWTs fails, the XRC is assumed to operate at 50%. The power curve used is a 5MW HAWT power curve. At 50% capacity, the power curve is effectively a 2.5MW conventional HAWT producing exactly half the power of a 5MW HAWT. In future this will be updated with a more accurate XRC power curve when the input is available from deliverable 2.3
- Jack-Up Vessels (JUV) are hired on a fix-on-fail basis for vertical axis component replacements. JUV charter durations are 60 days long. It is assumed that JUVs are required to replace main bearings. This is an important assumption because main bearing failures significantly increases the number of JUV charters required for the XRC. However, research is ongoing into the design of an easy removal mechanism for the main bearing, which would allow removal and replacement via an SOV, removing these additional JUV costs. The assumption is therefore a conservative one.

A key difference between D6.1 and D6.2 scenarios are that FSVs were replaced with SOVs. While FSVs have adequate deck space for secondary HAWT nacelles, often they do not have on-board cranes with the necessary weight requirements. Along with the replacement of an FSV with an SOV, the charter strategy also changed. Instead of hiring an FSV for the lifetime of the project, now SOVs are hired on a fix-on-fail basis. This was done to mitigate the increase in cost that comes with the change from FSV to SOV. Another difference is that the number of CTVs was increased from 4 to 5 for D6.2 and the JUV day rate and mobilisation cost was increased significantly based on discussions and review of estimates in the existing literature. Table 3.3 provides an overview of the vessels and vessel costs utilised in D6.1 and D6.2.

Table 3.3 Vessels – comparison D6.1 and D6.2

D6.1	Vessel	D6.2
4,000	CTV	4,000
Not Included	SOV	30,000
9,500	FSV	Not Included
400,000	JUV mob cost	800,000
50,000	JUV day rate	200,000

The O&M tool estimates variable O&M costs and energy production considering downtime due to failures. However, since the model focuses on the turbine, additional maintenance costs for the BoS (e.g. substructure, electrical etc.) have been added. These were calculated as 34% of the total maintenance costs for the baseline scenario based on the breakdown in (BVG Associates, 2019).¹ An annual fixed O&M cost of €13.65million is also included in the final OPEX based on (Stehly & Duffy, 2022). This accounts for fixed operations expenditure such as office rental space, insurance etc.

¹ This figure remains fixed for future sensitivity analysis.

3.4 Financial assumptions

As outlined in section 2.3, the discount rate can be quite a subjective estimate and determined in a number of ways. (Stehly & Duffy, 2022) apply a real WACC discount rate considering the assumptions summarised in Figure 3.3.

Financials			
Project design life	Years	25	Offshore wind project life for GPRA reporting
Tax Rate (combined state and federal)	%	26%	Feldman et al. 2020 and NREL's Annual Technology Baseline, updated with data from industry partners
Inflation rate	%	2.5%	
Debt fraction	%	67%	
Debt interest rate (nominal)	%	4.0%	
Return on equity (nominal)	%	10.0%	
WACC (nominal; after-tax)	%	5.3%	Calculation
WACC (real; after-tax)	%	2.7%	
Capital recovery factor (nominal; after-tax)	%	7.3%	
Capital recovery factor (real; after-tax)	%	5.6%	
Depreciable basis	%	100%	Simplified depreciation schedule
Depreciation schedule		5-year MACRS	Standard for U.S. wind projects
Depreciation adjustment (NPV)	%	86.8%	Calculation
Project finance factor	%	105%	
FCR (nominal)	%	7.6%	
FCR (real)	%	5.8%	

NREL

Figure 3.3 NREL study financial assumptions for fixed offshore wind reference farm

Using similar assumptions (outlined in Table 3.4), a pre-tax real WACC of 3.22% was determined for the XRC baseline scenario. As per section 2.8, tax is not considered in the X-Rotor LCoE tool calculation and therefore a pre-tax WACC is applied to the cash flow. The discount rate is also slightly lower than the equivalent pre-tax WACC for the NREL study (3.4%) due to the debt:equity breakdown assumed for the XRC baseline (70:30).

Table 3.4 Financial assumption comparison

Financial Assumption	NREL	XROTOR
Debt %	67%	70%
Cost of equity	10%	10%
Cost of debt	4%	4%
Inflation rate	2.50%	2.50%
Tax rate	26.00%	N/A
Pre-tax WACC nominal	5.98%	5.80%
Pre-tax WACC real	3.40%	3.22%
After-tax WACC nominal	5.28%	N/A
After-tax WACC real	2.72%	N/A

4 Baseline Scenario – Results

The estimated LCoE for the baseline scenario outlined in section 3 is €82.79/MWh. Table 4.1 provides a full summary of the XRC baseline scenario results.

Table 4.1 XRC Baseline Scenario – results summary

Project Results Summary		
Project Costs	€	3,242m
Discounted Project Costs	€	2,628m
Energy Production	GWh	43,535
Discounted Energy	GWh	31,737
Real LCOE	€/MWh	82.79

Figure 4.1 places the X-Rotor LCoE in the context of the current literature comparing results with

- the NREL LCoE estimate (Stehly & Duffy, 2022) using 2021 cost figures for a 600MW fixed offshore wind reference farm using 8MW turbines.
- the BEIS report estimate (Department of Business, 2020), assuming 2025 project commissioning for 1GW farm using 12MW turbines.

This allows a “validation” of results, determining whether they are reasonable within the context of existing LCoE estimates for fixed offshore wind, or where there may be significant under/over-estimates or issues with the current baseline XRC farm assumptions.

Figure 4.1 5MW X-Rotor Baseline – Results Comparison

It is clear from this comparison that the XRC baseline scenario results in a higher LCoE than the NREL and BEIS study. However it is clear from Table 4.2 this comparison is not based on like for like scenarios. The primary differences are presented in Table 4.2 and evaluated in the remainder of this section.

Table 4.2 Detailed LCoE comparison²

		X- Rotor	NREL	BEIS
Farm capacity (MW)	MW	500	600	1,000
Commissioning date	year	2021	2021	2025
Turbine rating (MW)	MW	5	8	12
Turbine number	number	100	75	83
Project lifetime (years)	years	20	25	30
Capacity factor	%	50%	49%	51%
Availability	%	89%	unknown	unknown
Discount Rate	%	3.2%	2.7%	6.3%
DR method	text	pre-tax real WACC	after-tax real WACC	pre-tax real IRR
Development and project management	€/kW	83	83	151
Turbine	€/kW	1,182	1,184	2,140
Electrical infrastructure	€/kW	631	631	
Substructure and foundation	€/kW	451	451	
Contingency, construction finance, insurance during construction	€/kW	502	502	
Assembly and installation	€/kW	371	371	
Lease price	€/kW	162	162	
Plant commissioning	€/kW	31	31	
Decommissioning	€/kW	106	106	
Total CAPEX	€/kW	3,437	3,439	2,291
Annual O&M - fixed	€/kW/yr	27	27	111
Annual O&M - variable	€/kW/yr	88	74	16
Total OPEX	€/kW/yr	115	101	127

² Exchange rates applied based on April 2023: \$1=€0.91 and £1=€1.16

Energy production	MWh/M W/yr	4,354	4,295	4,468
LCoE	€/MWh	82.79	70.98	66.12

Firstly, it is important to acknowledge that all three LCoE estimates use a slightly different calculation methodology. In particular, the BEIS report applies a higher discount rate since it is based on the IRR and does not consider tax or loan repayments. An IRR-based discount rate is usually higher than a WACC discount rate since it is the rate of return an investor would like in order to invest, rather than just to cover the cost of capital (see section 2.3 for further information). The NREL and X-Rotor scenarios use a similar method i.e. a WACC-based discount rate, although the XRC and NREL studies consider a pre-tax and after-tax scenario respectively (the latter includes a capital recovery factor and a 5-year MACRS depreciation schedule (Stehly & Duffy, 2022)). However, if a lower pre-tax real WACC discount rate was applied to the BEIS, (even including additional elements e.g. loan repayments) it would likely further reduce the LCoE estimate. If the NREL method removed tax, a higher pre-tax WACC would be applied to the LCoE, so it is likely to remain approximately the same. Therefore, **the baseline XRC scenario remains higher than the NREL and BEIS studies.**

The BEIS study has significant differences in the definition of the costs, making it difficult for full comparison. However, the annual O&M costs (€127/kW/yr) are significantly higher than the XRC or NREL studies. Within the BEIS estimate, the variable annual O&M cost is much lower than the fixed, while the opposite is true for the XRC and NREL studies. This might be due to a different definition for the BEIS study, but it is not clear what is included from (Department of Business, 2020). The CAPEX is significantly lower than the XRC and NREL studies, this may be due to economies of plant and turbine scaling.

The key variations between the XRC baseline and the NREL study are:

- the XRC turbine CAPEX/kW is marginally lower.
- the XRC variable annual O&M is 19% higher.
- The annual energy production (MWh/MW) is slightly higher.

Despite the close comparison between results, the XRC LCoE is 17% higher than the NREL study. This could be due to the lower OPEX costs, that have not been offset by the higher production for the XRC. It could also be due to the small differences in the financial assumption or unknown variables (e.g. the loan repayment period is not specified in (Stehly & Duffy, 2022)). However, it is likely that the most significant factors resulting in lower LCoE for the NREL and BEIS studies is the longer project lifetimes (NREL – 25 years and BEIS – 30 years), and economies of scale when increasing farm capacity using fewer, larger turbines. This deliverable will seek to “level the playing field” in section 5 by **updating the baseline project commissioning year to 2030** and applying cost reduction pathways that consider likely improvements in CAPEX (based on expected plant economies of scale as well as turbine scaling), OPEX (due to reduced maintenance requirements, improved strategies, and equipment such as vessel capabilities) and Annual Energy Production (increased availability due to improved O&M). Section 5 will also **apply 25 and 30-year project lifetimes** to the XRC scenario. This will provide a more equitable comparison with the 2030 estimates in the NREL and BEIS studies.

It should be noted that while the **XRC turbine CAPEX is very close to the NREL study**, a key aim of the design is to reduce CAPEX (see introduction). Therefore, this should be an **area for further optimisation**. This is partially done via the cost reduction pathways in section 5. However, a **more detailed and XROTOR specific CAPEX estimate will also be done for the next deliverable (D6.3)** as concept details are advanced in other work packages.

The project aims to investigate the advantages of the XRC in terms of O&M. The potential for low OPEX comes mainly from removing the gearbox and situating the non multi-pole lower cost

generators closer to sea level. This removes the requirement of a JUV for drive train component replacements. Instead, the market of cheaper SOVs can be exploited for this purpose. A measure of redundancy in the system also contributes to strong energy production. Since the turbine remains operational at 50% capacity when a secondary HAWT module component fails, it mitigates the impact of those failures on energy production. Results indicate that **the baseline XRC scenario has a higher variable maintenance cost than the validation figures** (NREL and BEIS) despite the fewer high-failure components and cheaper vessels. Interestingly, **the XRC does appear to have good energy production, despite achieving a relatively low availability of 89%** (an availability >95% is generally expected for fixed offshore wind). The availability % for the NREL and BEIS studies are unknown, although the XRC achieves a similar capacity factor (50%) to these studies (NREL 49%; BEIS 51%). Assuming the NREL and BEIS are assuming c.95% percentage as expected for fixed offshore wind, the high production and capacity factor achieved implies the XRC has great potential if a similar availability could be achieved. This is likely due to the in-built redundancy when the secondary rotor fails. Therefore, it is likely that by maximising production through a more optimistic O&M strategy, device reliability and site accessibility, the expected LCoE savings could become more apparent. Section 5 will seek to apply a **partially optimised O&M strategy** and assessing the potential impact of **moving the farm closer to shore**, aiming to reduce costs and increase production.

5 Sensitivity Analysis

This section will take the baseline scenario and apply sensitivity studies to a) assess the level of impact different assumptions have on results and b) determine realistic improvements to the original baseline scenario to apply to the final LCoE estimate in section 6. Each study takes the results of the previous section and applies further analysis on an iterative basis.

5.1 Project commissioning date

(Stehly & Duffy, 2022) provides the US Government Performance Result Act (GPRA) cost reduction pathway for fixed-offshore wind from 2018-2030. This is illustrated in Figure 5.1 and includes:

- 22% reduction in CAPEX through wind plant economies of scale, turbine scaling, export/array cables with less material use, and optimized foundation design.
- 19% increase in Annual Energy Production (AEP) through turbine scaling, enhanced control strategies, reduced wind plant losses, and higher availability due to improved vessel access.
- 54% reduction in OPEX due to advanced O&M strategies, improved vessel accessibility, and remote maintenance strategies (Stehly & Duffy, 2022).

Figure 5.1 Cost Reduction Pathways for fixed-bottom offshore wind from 2018-2030

To convert the XRC baseline to 2030 figures, this pathway was applied, assuming reduced percentages since the XRC figures used from this study are assumed to be based on 2021 costs. A CAPEX reduction of 16.5%; an OPEX reduction of 22.5% and an AEP increase of 14.25% were calculated, assuming a linear cost reduction/AEP increase per year from 2022-2030.

The NREL and BEIS reports estimate LCoEs of €46.41/MWh and €54.52/MWh respectively for a fixed offshore wind farm commissioned in 2030. Table 5.1 presents the 2021 and 2030 results for the XRC baseline. Figure 5.2 illustrates results in the context of the NREL and BEIS 2030 reference farms.

Table 5.1 XRC 2030 scenario results

	CAPEX (€bn)	Annual OPEX (€m)	Annual Energy Production (MWh)	Availability (%)	LCoE (€/MWh)
1. XRC Baseline	1.7	57.45	2,176,752	89.29	82.79
1.1. XRC 2030	1.4	34.18	2,486,939	89.29	64.44

Figure 5.2 5MW X-Rotor – 2030 - Results Comparison

An XRC project commissioned in 2030 results in an **LCoE of €64.44/MWh**. This is still significantly higher than the BEIS and NREL study. Therefore, section 5.2 continues to adjust the scenario to compare like-for-like by examining a 25 year and 30-year scenario.

5.2 Project lifetime

The baseline scenario assumes an operational project lifetime of 20 years. However, studies commonly assume at least a 25-year period (Stehly & Duffy, 2022) or even 30 years (Department of Business, 2020). Figure 5.3 demonstrates the potential LCoE reduction that could occur by extending the project lifetime for the 2030 XRC scenario 1.1, achieving an LCoE of €58.71/MWh and €54.99/MWh accordingly. This assumption proves extremely significant, resulting in an almost cost-competitive LCoE for the XRC with BEIS for the 30-year project, although the 25-year XRC project remains higher than the NREL study.

Figure 5.3 5MW X-Rotor – 2030 – Project Lifetime

Further optimisation in terms of O&M strategy and distance from shore are applied in section 5.3 and 5.4 to find further LCoE reductions.

5.3 Partially optimised O&M strategy

The O&M strategy for the baseline scenario is considered quite conservative. A partially optimised O&M scenario was also applied assuming:

- 70% capacity when the secondary rotor fails. Early work indicates that this may be a more realistic estimate for XRC capacity when one secondary HAWT fails;
- Using SOVs for main bearing replacements, which are cheaper than JUVs. This assumes the XRC is equipped with an easy removal mechanism for the main bearing;
- Reducing the replacement rate of the generator by 20, reducing the combined failure rate from 0.014 to 0.0112 failures per turbine per year. This amounts to around 3 fewer SOV charters over the lifetime of the project.

Results are presented in Table 5.2. They show a significant reduction to an LCoE of €50.55/MWh. This lies comfortably within the “validation range” of the NREL and BEIS studies (€46.41-54.52/MWh).

Table 5.2 XRC scenario results – partially optimised O&M

	Annual OPEX (€m)	Annual Energy Production (MWh)	Availability (%)	LCoE (€/MWh)
1.1 XRC 2030 30-year	34.18	2,486,939	89.29%	54.99
2.1 XRC 2030 30-year - Opt OM	28.11	2,503,545	89.86%	50.55

Figure 5.4 illustrates results in the context of the NREL and BEIS studies.

Figure 5.4 5MW X-Rotor – 2030 – Partially optimised O&M

5.4 Site location – distance from shore

The baseline distance from shore is 100km. According to (Díaz & Soares, 2020), the average distance from shore of offshore wind farms installed in Europe is 23.3km and the global average is 18.8km. Figure 5.5 illustrates the average water depth and distance from shore of operational wind farms (as of 2020).

Figure 5.5 Average water depth and distance from shore of operational offshore wind farms.³ (Díaz & Soares, 2020)

Therefore, this sensitivity study reduces the distance to shore of the XRC farm to 40km. Results are presented in Table 5.3 and illustrated in Figure 5.6.

Table 5.3 XRC scenario results – Distance to shore

	Annual OPEX (€m)	Annual Energy Production (MWh)	Availability (%)	LCoE (€/MWh)
1.1 XRC 2030 30-year	34.18	2,486,939	89.29%	54.99
3.1. XRC 2030 30-year - 40km	33.88	2,757,072	94.6%	49.42

³ The circle size represents the number of wind farms.

Figure 5.6 5MW X-Rotor – 2030 – Distance to Shore

This results in a slightly lower LCoE (€49.42/MWh) than the partially optimised O&M study (scenario 2.1) in section 5.3 (€50.55/MWh). Interestingly, the reduction is achieved by **reducing the O&M costs in scenario 2.1** due to reduced failures and the use of lower cost vessels. Reducing the distance from shore (**scenario 3.1**) **increases energy production** and availability due to improved site accessibility since the shorter distance means less time and shorter weather windows are required to get to site and undertake maintenance. A combined optimised scenario (4.1) was run to assess the potential total reduction in LCoE (section 5.5).

5.5 Combined O&M strategy and 40km from shore

The partially optimised O&M strategy (section 5.3) and reducing the farm distance from shore from 100km to 40km (section 5.4) combined to reduce the **XRC LCoE to €47.39/MWh**. Results are presented in Table 5.4 and illustrated in Figure 5.7.

Table 5.4 XRC scenario results – combined partially optimised O&M strategy and reduced distance from shore

	Annual OPEX (€m)	Annual Energy Production (MWh)	Availability (%)	LCoE (€/MWh)
1.1 XRC 2030 30-year	34.18	2,486,939	89.29%	54.99
2.1 XRC 2030 30-year - Opt OM	28.11	2,503,545	89.86%	50.55
3.1. XRC 2030 30-year - 40km	33.88	2,757,072	94.6%	49.42
4.1 XRC 2030 30-year – Opt OM & 40km	27.69	2,655,951	94.91%	47.39

Figure 5.7 5MW X-Rotor – 2030 – Combined Sensitivity Studies

Scenario 4.1 achieves an availability of almost 95%, increasing energy production as well as reducing annual OPEX. This scenario brings the XRC much more in line with expectations (NREL and BEIS studies). However, further optimisations should still be considered, particularly the XRC turbine

CAPEX. This will be reviewed in more detail in the next deliverable (D6.3) when XROTOR specific CAPEX inputs are available.

Scenario 4.1 is taken forward as the XRC baseline scenario assuming a 30-year project, commissioned in 2030 with a partially optimised O&M scenario, 40km from shore. Therefore, new baseline LCoE for further sensitivity analysis is €47.39/MWh.

5.6 Financial assumptions

5.6.1 Discount rate

Table 5.5 summarises a series of sensitivity studies undertaken, which vary the discount rate (pre-tax real WACC) applied to scenario 4.1 (LCoE €47.39/MWh established in section 5.5). The table highlights the variations applied to increase/decrease the WACC including:

- The debt:equity ratio (scenario 4.2 and 4.21)
- The inflation rate (scenario 4.22 and 4.23)
- The cost of equity (scenario 4.24)
- The cost of debt (scenario 4.25)

Table 5.5 Discount Rate Scenarios

Scenario	4.1	4.2	4.21	4.22	4.23	4.24	4.25
Debt %	70%	67%	73%	70%	70%	70%	70%
Cost of equity %	10%	10%	10%	10%	10%	12%	10%
Cost of debt %	4%	4%	4%	4%	4%	4%	3%
Inflation rate %	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%	2.00%	3.00%	2.50%	2.50%
Pre-tax WACC nominal %	5.80%	5.98%	5.62%	5.80%	5.80%	6.40%	5.10%
Pre-tax WACC real %	3.22%	3.40%	3.04%	3.73%	2.72%	3.80%	2.54%
LCoE €/MWh	47.39	47.72	47.05	48.36	46.42	48.52	46.07

Figure 5.8 illustrates the impact increasing/decreasing the discount rate (WACC) has on the LCoE.

Figure 5.8 Impact of discount rate

Overall variations achieve a 2%/3% increase/decrease on LCoE. Therefore, these assumptions are significant and should be considered when reviewing results.

5.6.2 Loan repayment schedule

The current baseline scenario assumes a 30-year project lifetime and an 18-year loan repayment schedule (60% of the project lifetime) starting in year 1. However, this is an uncertain assumption that could vary for each project. Therefore, Figure 5.9 presents sensitivity analysis varying this assumption for scenario 4.1, to demonstrate how this can affect the LCoE.

Figure 5.9 Impact of Loan Repayment Term

5.6.3 Vessel costs

All previous scenarios consider fixed hire vessel costs as outlined in section 3.3. However, this is a very uncertain assumption that will depend on numerous factors e.g. the availability of a given vessel when required or the vessel hire contractual arrangements e.g. duration of hire, seasonal hire etc. To illustrate the potential impact of this uncertain factor, a scenario was run that reduced the CTV day rates from €4,000 to €3,000. This results in quite a reduction in the LCoE from €47.39 to €46.71/MWh, demonstrating the significant impact such uncertain factors could have on results.

5.6.4 CAPEX

CAPEX estimates have a significant impact on the project LCoE. This is demonstrated in Figure 5.10 where a variation of +/- 15% (in 5% increments) results in an LCoE range of €42.09-52.68/MWh. This is 11% above and below scenario 4.1 LCoE estimate (€47.39/MWh). Given the uncertainty of the CAPEX estimates, this variation must be considered in the final estimated LCoE for the XRC in section 6.

Figure 5.10 Impact of CAPEX estimates

6 XRC LCoE estimate

The final LCoE estimate is based on scenario 4.1, commissioned in 2030 and with a 30-year project lifetime. As demonstrated in Section 5.6, financial assumptions could significantly impact the LCoE estimate. Therefore, an LCoE range of €43.05-50.44/MWh with an average of €46.74/MWh has been determined for the XRC based upon combinations of the lowest and highest financial assumptions, as detailed in Table 6.1.

Table 6.1

Scenario	WACC	Loan Period	CTV cost	CAPEX variation	LCoE	LCoE Variation
4.1	3.22%	18	€4,000	0%	47.39	0%
Lowest	2.54%	12	€3,000	-5%	43.05	-9%
Highest	3.80%	24	€4,000	+5%	50.44	17%
				Average	46.74	-7%

Results illustrated in the context of the NREL and BEIS studies for validation in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.1 5MW X-Rotor – 2030 – LCoE estimated range.

The XRC LCoE average (€46.74/MWh) and highest (€50.44/MWh) estimates lie within the NREL and BEIS LCoE “validation range” (€46.41-54.42/MWh), indicating that results are reasonable. It is expected that the BEIS report LCoE is significantly higher than the XRC and NREL estimates. As

outlined in section 4, this is because the BEIS report applies a higher discount rate based on IRR rather than WACC. While this inevitably results in a higher LCoE, it is useful to consider the BEIS estimate as the higher end of the LCoE range for a 2030 fixed Offshore Wind Farm cost estimate. It is also expected that the average XRC LCoE is close to the NREL estimate, given the majority of case study costs and financial assumptions were based on (Stehly & Duffy, 2022). The lowest XRC LCoE (€43.05/MWh) is below the “validation range.” This may suggest that the concept has significant cost saving potential. The next step is to determine whether this is the case by applying the same assumptions, calculation methods and models to traditional HAWTs (geared and direct drive). This will be done in D6.3 to determine if, where and to what extent the XRC provides LCoE savings.

7 Conclusion

This deliverable (D6.2) has developed a baseline XRC case study of 100 x 5MW turbines, 100km from shore, based on present day figures (2021) and with a 20-year lifetime. The report applies a series of cost estimates based on figures in the current literature. The University of Strathclyde’s O&M model provides the maintenance costs and annual energy production estimate. Additional operational costs were added based on figures in the current literature. A set of financial assumptions (inflation rate, debt:equity ratio) were used to determine a WACC-based discount rate derived from (Stehly & Duffy, 2022) figures to facilitate project comparison and validation. The deliverable undertakes a number of sensitivity studies to test and review the baseline XRC LCoE estimate (€82.79) including:

- Applying a cost reduction pathway based on (Stehly & Duffy, 2022) to convert present day costs to 2030 figures considering economies of plant and turbine scaling; expected savings in O&M due to improved strategies, vessel operational capabilities; and likely improvement in energy production due to O&M optimisations.
- A 25 and 30-year project lifetime.
- A partially optimised O&M strategy.
- Reducing the distance from shore to 40km.

An updated baseline assuming a 30-year project, commissioned in 2030, with a partially optimised O&M strategy and 40km from shore resulted in an LCoE of €47.39. Given the uncertainty and project-specific nature of the financial assumptions, a number of variations were applied to determine a final XRC LCoE range. The following parameters were varied:

- the WACC (discount rate);
- the loan repayment schedule;
- vessel costs (CTV day-rate);
- CAPEX.

Based on the above methodology, D6.2 has successfully determined an estimated LCoE range for the XRC (€43.05-50.44/MWh). Results were validated against the NREL and BEIS reports for fixed offshore wind turbines (commissioned in 2030), indicating that they are reasonable estimates and that the XRC has potential to provide cost savings. Key optimisation areas identified as significantly impacting LCoE include the CAPEX; maximising production by improving site accessibility and availability; minimising OPEX, although not at the expense of project energy production availability.

It should be noted that the XRC LCoE estimate is based on the current information available in literature at this time. This will be further reviewed and updated for the next deliverable (D6.3) once XROTOR specific inputs are available from other work packages. It is expected that the next report will consider:

- an updated CAPEX for the XRC turbine,

- a new power curve,
- possibly updated failure rates and O&M costs.

D6.3 will then apply the same assumptions, methodology and models to determine LCoE estimates for traditional HAWTs (geared and direct drive train). This will allow the project to assess whether and to what extent the XRC can provide LCoE savings as well as where the most significant reductions occur or could occur, driving future design iterations.

8 References

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